

Optimized CAD System for Breast Cancer Detection with Tabu Search and RNN

Syrine Neffati¹ et Mohsen Machhout²

¹ Faculty of Sciences of Monastir,
Electronics and Micro-Electronic Laboratory (LEME),
University of Monastir, Monastir 5000, Tunisia
Syrine.neffati@gmail.com

² Faculty of Sciences of Monastir,
Electronics and Micro-Electronic Laboratory (LEME),
University of Monastir, Monastir 5000, Tunisia
mohsen.machhout@fsm.rnu.tn

Abstract Breast cancer is the second leading cause of cancer-related deaths among women and the most common type of noncutaneous malignancy worldwide. It currently affects more than one in ten women globally. New approaches and strategies are continuously being developed to improve breast cancer prevention, survival rates, and mortality reduction. In this study, we propose a new optimized technique for detecting and classifying breast cancer called TKPCA, which combines the Tabu search algorithm and Kernel Principal Component Analysis. To implement TKPCA, we use a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to build a classifier named TKPCA-RNN, which can differentiate between benign and malignant tissue in images. The Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset (WBCD) and Wisconsin Diagnosis Breast Cancer (WDBC) were used as two breast cancer databases from the UCI benchmark repository. Our experiments showed that our proposed method performed better than other well-known classifiers, which is an impressive result.

Key words Breast cancer; RNN; KPCA; Kernel Principal Component Analysis; pattern recognition; optimization;

1 Introduction

Early detection of Breast Cancer (BC) is crucial in reducing mortality rates associated with this disease [1]. BC is the most common invasive cancer in women and is the second leading cause of death after lung cancer [1]. Globally, BC accounts for more than one million cases and nearly 600,000 deaths each year, making it the most common invasive cancer in women [2]. With the rise of machine learning techniques in medical and biomedical fields, computer-aided diagnosis systems have become more effective in providing a second opinion to radiologists and decision makers [3]. These techniques have numerous benefits, including reducing treatment costs, enhancing clinical studies, and improving patient outcomes [4].

Several data mining techniques have been suggested for supervised machine learning approaches. However, selecting an appropriate method for use as a computer-aided diagnosis system can be a challenge. Additionally, these techniques are commonly applied in real image classification [5]. To address this, we introduce a novel computer-aided diagnosis system for breast cancer classification

that employs an optimized classification system. In our study, we propose a computer-aided diagnosis system for breast cancer classification that utilizes an optimized Kernel Principal Component Analysis (KPCA) for dimensionality reduction and a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). We have named the suggested algorithm TKPCA-RNN.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section two provides an overview of the methodology utilized. Section three contains information regarding the dataset used in this study. Section four outlines the TKPCA approach used as a feature extraction and dimensionality detection technique. Section five details the classifier utilized (RNN). Section six presents the study's findings. Finally, in section seven, we conclude the paper.

2 Proposed methodology

This research work is based on three fundamental phases: (1) preprocessing, (2) dimensionality reduction and (3) classification. The three phases are described in Figure 1.

Figure 1 : Methodology of the TKPCA-RNN method

3 Breast cancer dataset

The breast cancer data used in this research was downloaded from the UCI Machine Learning Repository [6]. Two databases were used, the Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset (WBCD) [7] and the Wisconsin Diagnosis Breast Cancer (WDBC) database [8].

The WBCD and WDBC benchmarks have been widely used by researchers to test their computer-aided diagnosis systems for breast cancer. In this proposed work, our new algorithm was tested on these databases, and remarkable results were achieved. Details of the benchmarks used can be found in Table 1 and the following subsections.

Table 1 : Details about benchmarks WBCD and WDCB

Dataset	WBCD	WDCB
No. of attributes	10	31
No. of instances	699	569
Class 1 (Benign)	458	357
Class 2 (Malignant)	241	212

3.1 Wisconsin Breast Cancer Database (WBCD)

The database contains 699 instances and 10 attributes, including the class attribute. The classes are divided into benign or malignant. Each attribute is assigned a number from 1 to 10, and these features are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Features of WBCD database

No. of Feature	Features of WBCD
1	uniformity of cell size
2	clump thickness
3	uniformity of cell shape
4	bare nuclei
5	marginal adhesion
6	single epithelial cell size
7	Mitosis
8	bland chromatin
9	normal nuclei

3.2 Wisconsin Diagnosis Breast Cancer (WDBC)

The WDBC database consists of 569 instances, including 31 attributes with the class attribute included. The classes are divided into benign or malignant. The attribute characterization is based on ten features calculated for each cell nucleus [9], and the features are listed in Table 3. These features define and characterize the properties of each cell nucleus in the image [9]. The mean, standard error, and three largest values are computed for all the images, resulting in a total of 30 features.

Table 3: Features of WDBC database

No. of Feature	Features of WDBC
1	Texture, Radius
2	Perimeter
3	Smoothness
4	Area
5	Concavity
6	Compactness
7	Symmetry
8	Concave points
9	Fractal dimension

4. Optimized KPCA for dimensionality reduction

This study proposes a new technique for efficient dimensionality reduction, which is based on KPCA and Tabu search algorithms and is named TKPCA.

4.1 KPCA

The KPCA technique is a nonlinear form of PCA that enables nonlinear dimensionality reduction by transforming the information with a nonlinear transformation into a new subspace [3, 4].

In this research work, KPCA is used as a feature reduction technique. We apply PCA to a higher subspace after transforming the data using the kernel, which is known as the kernel trick. The resulting PCA is given by the following equation:

$$\overset{\circ}{C} = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{i=1}^l \phi(x_i) \phi(x_i)^T \quad (1)$$

from input variables $x_i \in R^n$ we take only the non-linear centered information noted $\phi(x_i)$

$$\lambda V = \overset{\circ}{C} V, V \in F, \lambda \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

All the solutions V with $\lambda \geq 0$ are in the range of $\Phi(x_1), \Phi(x_2), \dots, \Phi(x_l)$. The issue is described as follows:

$$n\lambda\alpha = K\alpha \quad (3)$$

le α be the column vectors such as: $V = \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i \Phi(x_i)$ and let K be the kernel-matrix that verifies the following situation

$$\begin{aligned} \iint K(x_1, x_2) h(x_1) h(x_2) dx_1 dx_2 &> 0 \\ \int h^2(x_1) dx_1 &< \infty \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $K(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \alpha_i \psi(x) \psi(y)$, $\alpha_i \geq 0$. Let us compute the k^{th} non-linear principal components of x as the projections of $\phi(x)$ onto the eigenvectors V^k

$$\beta(y)_k = V^k \phi(y) = \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i^k K(y_i, y) \quad (5)$$

We select the first few nonlinear components that retain the desired percentage of data variance. The resulting data is then reduced accordingly.

4.2 Tabu search algorithm

The main goal of this work is to determine an optimal KPCA method. Therefore, we utilize the Tabu search algorithm to select the optimal value for the kernel parameter of the Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel used. The initial solution of the Tabu search algorithm is randomly selected, taking into account the constraints of the parameter σ (the kernel's parameter), which was initially set to be within the range of $[2^{-6}, 2^6]$. The solution is computed by adding the closest unused neighbor values of to the current solution, and testing if they improve the classification accuracy. The process is repeated until all the neighbors are visited. At the end, the optimal value of $\{h_1, \dots, h_k\}$ is selected.

5 Recurrent Neural Network

Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) become very popular in recent years as they are capable of handling instructed information. The variable-length sequence is the general input to RNN $x = \{x_1, \dots, x_T\}$ where $x_i \in R^d$ and d is the dimension of x_i . The RNN maintain the internal hidden state h , that become a hidden sequence of $\{h_1, \dots, h_k\}$. The RNN treatment a certain step t is as follows:

$$h_t = f(w_{xh}x_t + w_{hh}h_{t-1}), \quad (6)$$

$f(x)$ is considered the activation function. The weight between input layer x and hidden layer h is noted as the matrix w_{xh} and the hidden layer and itself is the matrix w_{hh} .

We calculate the output of RNN as follows:

$$y_t = w_{hy}h_t, \quad (7)$$

The matrix of weight between hidden layer h and the output y is the matrix w_{hy} .

6. Experiments and results

6.1 Performance Evaluation Criteria

There are different classification algorithms in data mining. To evaluate their performance, different criteria need to be taken into consideration to compare and analyze each method [10, 11]. In this study, we used the RBF kernel with KPCA as a feature reduction technique. To evaluate the results, we utilized the confusion matrix, which is a tool to measure the performance of the classifier (Table 4). According to Table 4, TP (True Positive) represents the number of malignant BC images that were correctly classified as malignant by the classifier, FN (False Negative) represents the number of malignant BC images that were wrongly classified as benign by the classifier. TN (True Negative) represents the number of benign BC images that were correctly classified as benign by the classifier. Finally, FP (False Positive) represents the number of benign BC images that were wrongly classified as malignant by the classifier.

Table 4: General form of confusion matrix [11]

		Prediction		Total
		Yes	No	
Actual	Yes	TP	FN	TP + FN
	No	FP	TN	FP + TN
Total		TP + FP	FN + TN	

6.2 Results and discussion

It is very important in data mining to achieve a high accuracy rate. It is the key performance metric that will indicate that the classifier is reliable. And since we are working with relatively small datasets, we have opted for k-fold cross-validation to generalize our results to other databases. We have utilized 10-fold cross-validation in this study. The results of the first run of cross-validation for both benchmarks are given in Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5: Results of the first run of cross validation for dataset WBCD

	Malignant	Benign
Malignant	99.5	0.5
Benign	1.1	98.9

Table 6: Results of the first run of cross validation for dataset WDBC

	Malignant	Benign
Malignant	99.2	0.8
Benign	0.6	99.4

From tables 5 and 6 we remark that we have obtained during the first run of cross validation 99.2% as a total accuracy rate for dataset WBCD and 99.3 % as a total accuracy rate for dataset WDBC.

The findings presented in tables 7 and 8 are evaluated in terms of accuracy, specificity and sensitivity. According to these tables we have obtained 99.1 % as an accuracy rate for dataset WBCD and 99.5% as an accuracy rate for dataset WDBC.

Table 7: Classification results compared to other datasets for database WBCD

Method	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
TKPCA + RNN	99.1 %	99.1 %	99.2 %
PCA+RNN	95.6%	95.7 %	95.5%
LDA+RNN	92.7%	92.8%	92.4 %
SVD+RNN	90.4 %	91.1 %	90.3 %

Table 8: Classification results compared to other datasets for database WDBC

Method	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
TKPCA + RNN	99.5 %	99.4 %	99.6 %
PCA+RNN	95.9%	95.8 %	95.7%
LDA+RNN	93.8%	93.7%	93.5 %
SVD+RNN	91.8 %	91.9 %	91.5 %

From the results in tables 7 and 8 we conclude that the proposed approach TKPCA-RNN for breast cancer detection gave the best results when compared to other well-known methods used as feature reduction techniques. This work proposes a new efficient algorithm to be used as a computer aided diagnosis system in general and breast cancer detector in particular.

7. Conclusion and future studies

In this study, we proposed a new computer-aided diagnosis system for breast cancer detection, in which we used a new optimized kernel method named TKPCA as a feature reduction technique, along with an RNN classifier. The proposed approach demonstrated highly accurate results in breast cancer detection and classification. In future studies, we will aim to apply this technique to larger datasets.

Références

- [1] Rathi, V. P., & Palani, S. (2012). Brain tumor MRI image classification with feature selection and extraction using linear discriminant analysis. arXiv preprint arXiv:1208.2128.
- [2] Arbyn, M., Weiderpass, E., Bruni, L., de Sanjosé, S., Saraiya, M., Ferlay, J., & Bray, F. (2020). Estimates of incidence and mortality of cervical cancer in 2018: a worldwide analysis. *The Lancet Global Health*, 8(2), e191-e203.
- [3] Neffati, S., Abdellafou, K. B., Taouali, O., & Bouzrara, K. (2019). A new Bio-CAD system based on the optimized KPCA for relevant feature selection. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 102(1-4), 1023-1034.
- [4] Neffati, S., Ben Abdellafou, K., Aljuhani, A., & Taouali, O. (2021). An enhanced CAD system based on machine Learning Algorithm for brain MRI classification. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 41(1), 1845-1854.
- [5] Nilashi, M., Ibrahim, O., Ahmadi, H., & Shahmoradi, L. (2017). A knowledge-based system for breast cancer classification using fuzzy logic method. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(4), 133-144.
- [6] URL : <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/index.php>
- [7] Mangasarian, O. L., Setiono, R., & Wolberg, W. H. (1990). Pattern recognition via linear programming: Theory and application to medical diagnosis. *Large-scale numerical optimization*, 22-31.
- [8] Mangasarian, O. L., Street, W. N., & Wolberg, W. H. (1995). Breast cancer diagnosis and prognosis via linear programming. *Operations Research*, 43(4), 570-577.
- [9] Salama, G. I., Abdelhalim, M., & Zeid, M. A. E. (2012). Breast cancer diagnosis on three different datasets using multi-classifiers. *Breast Cancer (WDBC)*, 32(569), 2.
- [10] Avci, E., Karakus, S., Ozmen, O., & Avci, D. (2018, March). Performance comparison of some classifiers on chronic kidney disease data. In *2018 6th International Symposium on Digital Forensic and Security (ISDFS)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [11] Talabani, H., & Engin, A. V. C. I. (2018, September). Performance comparison of SVM kernel types on child autism disease database. In *2018 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Data Processing (IDAP)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.